

ELECTRIC BATTERY MODELING AND DISCHARGE VOLTAGE PREDICTION USING
ADAPTIVE NEURO FUZZY INFERENCE SYSTEM (ANFIS)

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Abstract – This paper presents a model-based condition of electric battery during discharge with a certain load. The battery modelling equation was obtained from the typical battery model in MATLAB 2022a. This paper also presents the prediction of the remaining voltage condition of the electric battery based on two input parameters load and temperature using Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS). The time-series data was collected from the battery experiment that run the data from full voltage capacity into certain capacity in a period of time. The experiment used 5 different load condition and run about few hours.

Keywords— Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS); Model-based condition; energy storage devices; time-series prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy storage systems can help spread renewable energy sources for both off tied applications, as well as provide auxiliary functions including frequency regulation, spinning reserve, and voltage control, as well as potentially assisting in the future transition to the smart. Furthermore, we are in a time where electric vehicles and their dissemination are fast rising, and electric vehicle batteries are being used to inject energy into when needed (vehicle, V2G applications) all over the world [1].

Indeed, the battery-based storage system's energy efficiency is critical in lowering losses during energy transfer procedures. Non-unitary charging/discharging efficiency coefficients were studied in various articles dealing with battery charging/discharging strategies, but they were based on the assumption that [2].

Prediction of battery life is very important because it can be used to avoid battery draining suddenly causing interference. Disruption that often occurs in batteries which are temperature over time the use of which has impact on the decrease in the age of disposable batteries, so capacity use will also decrease. In addition to knowing the optimal and targeted settings, as well as knowledge about battery maintenance so that the electrical energy produced can be utilized optimally in battery

storage and can last a long time. Factors that can affect battery capacity are the rate of discharge and ambient temperature [3].

Batteries, including lithium-ion and lead-acid cells, degrade with time and during use, which results in a reduction in their ability to store energy and an increase in internal resistance. For both performance and financial reasons, it is crucial to be able to estimate a material's rate of degradation and remaining usable life (RUL). This is what drives our study in this article. For instance, the driveable range of an electric vehicle is closely correlated with the battery capacity. Predicting RUL at the design stage and during operation is essential for energy storage asset valuation, depreciation, warranty, second life value, insurance, and preventative maintenance purposes, and the investment case is highly dependent on the degradation profile. ANFIS technique, or adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system. For a collection of data, the ANFIS combines fuzzy logic with artificial neural networks and a learning method to determine the rules. ANFIS permits regulations to.

This study will examine the model-based condition of battery output power and voltage remaining prediction based on the parameters input and the ANFIS technique, or adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system. In the ANFIS approach is more effective for prediction than the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) network method because the error rate is lower [5]. In addition, the quantity and quality of the sample data have an impact on the accuracy of the ANFIS model [6].

The ANFIS method is a form of soft computing method which is combined with fuzzy logic (mathematical logic) and synthetic neural systems. ANFIS is an approach where in a learning algorithm's rules are established for a set of data so that ANFIS additionally permits the laws to adapt [7]. Several studies have been conducted with system analysis related to prediction using ANFIS with various different cases. As research conducted by Rezaeianzadeh [8] the study compared the use of ANN, ANFIS, MLR, and MNLR to predict the daily maximum flood flow in the Khosrow Shirin watershed, Iran. The results show that area-weighted rainfall is superior when applied as input to ANN and MNLR, while spatially varying rainfall inputs to ANFIS and MLR models show more accurate estimates.

ANFIS is selected because this method has been applied for battery prediction in Gaber [9], while other method has not been found. Another reason is because the ANFIS prediction is based on the if then rule mechanics using the membership function that is appropriate for small size prediction parameter and hence will provide faster training and testing process. And this research is continuations and improvement from previous studies.

II. METHODS

A. Model-based condition

An experiment to measure pulse discharge in a Lead Acid. MATLAB and Simulink were used to estimate a combination of model parameter values. The battery was initially completely charged at 12V. There was a two-hour rest period in between the pulse discharges to maintain the battery voltage. In light of these requirements, the test needs five data points to describe the

parameters of the battery model. The model the function is used to approximate the data to Figure 1.

Figure 1. Battery model.

The model is based on the Equation:

$$E = (1 - Loss)V - KQ_{max} \frac{1-s}{s} \tag{1}$$

where V is the battery constant voltage in Volts, K is the battery polarization resistance in Ohms, and E is the battery terminal voltage in Volts. Q_{max} is the highest possible battery capacity in Ampere-hours, and s , with 1 representing a fully charged battery and 0 representing a drained battery. The charging status of the battery is calculated from the current's integral in the battery with negative current signifying charging and positive current signifying discharge. the first instance of the battery is indicated by Q_0 based on amp-hours. The voltage drop is loss during charging, calculated as a percentage of the constant voltage of a battery. in the event that the discharges, this value is zero. This study only used the discharge only.

Battery used in this study has an electric charge of 70 Ah. The Loss value considered to be 0 since the experiment done in discharge condition. Initial battery charge (Q_0) is set at 6.5. by default. Battery polarization resistance (K) can be calculated using the following equation:

$$K = \frac{V_{bat}K}{I_{bat}} = \frac{V_{bat}}{I_{bat}} \tag{2}$$

The parameters information is displayed in Table. 1.

Table 1. Dimensional value of the experiment.

$Q_0(Ah)$	$Q_{max}(Ah)$	$V (Volt)$	$Loss (%)$
6.5	70	12	0

B. ANFIS prediction

ANFIS (an acronym for the "Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System" fuzzy logic and synthetic neural network hybrid (ANN). By utilizing the rule basis, Floppy logic offers benefits in representing the qualitative features of human understanding retrieval processes judgments. Without the requirement for modeling math, the ANN has benefits in spotting patterns, education, and training how to solve a challenge. And it can function with data that has been entered into it

in the past, as well as generate predictions about future events based on that data. ANFIS will not be able to do both until it possesses both skills [10]. The ANFIS approach contains five levels: a layer of fuzzification, a law layer, a layer normalization layer, and a layer defuzzification layer, and neuro results single [5].

Neuroadaptive learning is a technique. is comparable regards neural networks in terms of how it operates. The fuzzy modeling procedure can be learned using neuro-adaptive learning techniques A data set's description decides who is a member. An inference system is used to determine parameters for functions that permit the connected fuzzy logic to best follow the provided data input and output. It is possible to employ a system -like structure that resembles a neural network Inputs and outputs are mapped through membership functions and their associated input- membership functions for output, and then through elements of output, as well as related variables.

The specifics linked utilizing the membership features change during the method of education. These parameters' computation is done using aided by a vector gradient. These parameters' computation is aided by a gradient vector. This vector of gradient represents fuzziness of inference system performance predicts data for input and output for a specific set of parameters. After acquiring a gradient's direction, one multiple optimization strategies can be used to change the conditions and minimize some errors measurements. This mistake metric is frequently calculated using total of the square differences between the intended and actual outcomes. Least squares estimation and backpropagation are combined in ANFIS to estimate membership is a feature parameters.

The following are the properties of the ANFIS that is recommended:

1. The result is a Sugeno-type system of the zeroth order.
2. It generates employing weighted average defuzzification, a single output. The membership functions for output have all been fixed.
3. It does not follow the same set of rules. There must be an equal number of output membership functions as rules because different rules have different output membership functions.
4. Each rule is equally weighted.

Fuzzy logic by Sugeno model shown in Figure 4, while The architecture of ANFIS is shown in Figure 5, which contains layers for input, fuzzing, drawing conclusions, and defuzzing. The system consists of in the input layer, N neurons representing inputs, for each input, and F input membership functions represented by F*N neurons in the layer of fuzzification. The inference contains FN rules and FN neurons. One neuron and two levels of defuzzification make up the output layer. The fuzzy inference system under investigation is assumed to have Figure 2 depicts a system with two inputs (x and y) and one output (z). A popular two if-then rules with fuzziness for a rule set zero- Sugeno fuzzy model order is following is:

First rule: $f_1 = r_1$ if $x = A_1$ and $y = B_1$.

Rule 2: If x and y are both A2, then f2 equals r2.

Figure 2. Fuzzy logic model by Sugeno. Source: [11]

Figure 3. The ANFIS's architecture has two inputs and one output. Source: [12]

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this study, a battery monitoring device is built as presented in Figure 4. The device is composed of the battery, load, thermal load, voltage sensor, temperature sensor, current sensor, watt meter, voltage indicator, and current sensor. An overall experiment photo and a detail component of the battery monitoring is presented in Figure 5 and Table 2, respectively.

Figure 4. Battery monitoring device.

Figure 5. Component of battery monitoring device and wiring diagram flowchart.

Table 2. Battery information.

Battery brand	Luminous
Battery kind	Acidic lead
Battery power	12 Volt
Battery power	70 Ah
Dimension	42x19x23 cm

Prior to the experiment, a battery was fully charged up to around 12 Volt. A fully charge battery was connected to the different load and the battery monitoring data was collected during the discharge condition. In one experiment, it takes approximately 6-8 hours to obtain the discharge data from fully charge battery to empty capacity (in Volt).

Figure 6 presents an example of battery monitoring experiment for load equal to 180 Watt. Once the battery is connected as presented in Figure 4, the battery monitoring device is turn on. Inside the battery monitoring device panel, there is a 7 inch monitor for user interface and input parameter. This display monitoring is connected to the Raspberry Pi4. The user is expected to fill in the Load and Temperature input data before pressing the run button. Once the run button pressed, the data acquisition is started. This device has been previously program to automatically acquire the data during the discharge process in timely basis (every 30 seconds). The actual data every 30 seconds is showing in the output block in the user interface as presented in Figure 6. After few hours, the experiment is completed and the data is save in the excel format as also presented in Figure 6.

There are 4 different loads were tested in the battery condition monitoring device, i.e. 130, 180, 200, and 220 Watt. The data is then process in the model-based condition and also used for ANFIS prediction.

Due to limited battery available, this study only used 2 batteries during the experiment. One battery for training and another battery for testing. Two dataset were collected for training and one dataset was collected for testing. The battery is fully charge prior to the experiment and then connect to the determined load for discharging. The data is collected during a whole discharging process.

Figure 6. An example procedure of battery monitoring experiment for load 180 Watt.

The purpose of power source monitoring method is to run batteries from fully charge capacity to empty approximately less than 5 volt. In that case each experiment is takes about 6-8 hours depending on the load. Higher load will result to the less experimental hours. The discharge volt from four different loads were presented in Figure 7. This data will be proceed further for ANFIS training.

Figure 7. Discharge voltage data from four different load: (a) 130 Watt; (b) 180 Watt; (c) 200 Watt.

An example of data collection in excel file that shows the duration of experiment is presented in Figure 8. Please note that the middle part of data was hidden to show the beginning and the ending of discharge voltage.

According to the time-series data collection as presented in the Figure 8, the experiment is conducted on June 6th, 2022 at 14:58 or 2:58 pm (Jkt time). The experiment stop at 23:06 or 11:06 pm (Jkt time) and it has been operated about 8 hours. Load and Temperature (Temp) are the input parameters. For battery temperature (T Bat), battery power (V (I Bat), battery voltage (V Bat), and battery capacity (C Bat) are the output measurement. Battery was initially fully charge about 12 volt and it has been used for 8 hours for load 180 W until 5.41 volt.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date and Time	Load	Temp	T Bat	V Bat	I Bat	C Bat
2	22-06-27 14:58:59	180	35	31.28	12.42	1.23	94.81
3	22-06-27 14:59:29	180	35	34.62	12.42	1.17	94.65
4	22-06-27 14:59:59	180	35	38.63	12.18	1.1	85.53
5	22-06-27 15:00:29	180	35	38.63	12.09	6.64	82.19
6	22-06-27 15:00:59	180	35	35.72	12.09	6.54	82.34
972	22-06-27 23:04:53	180	35	31.04	5.52	2.04	0.99
973	22-06-27 23:05:23	180	35	32.71	5.5	2.08	0.99
974	22-06-27 23:05:53	180	35	32.01	5.47	1.95	0.99
975	22-06-27 23:06:23	180	35	37.59	5.44	2.03	0.99
976	22-06-27 23:06:53	180	35	38.42	5.41	1.93	0.99

Figure 8. Data collected for load 180 Watt.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Model-based condition

The simulation gives discharge curves which separated to determine voltage and current for each load. The experiments are conducted in discharged condition with no power supply present. After a load is put on, the voltage is reduced. There are two types of voltage drops: transient voltage drops and instantaneous voltage drops. It is possible to use the instantaneous voltage drop

to get the series resistor model parameter. Charging and discharging is commonly achieved by moving a switch that connects the capacitor between a power supply and a resistor.

MATLAB and Simulink were used to estimate a combination of model parameter values. The battery was initially completely charged at 12V. There was a two-hour rest period in between the pulse discharges to maintain the battery voltage. The voltage model used to approximate the data of load 130W, 180W, and 200W is presented Figure 9(a). A charge discharge curve of 130 watt load is presented Figure 9 (a). The voltage at discharge from the experiment was decreased from 12.87 V to 10.34 V in 10.67 hours and it significantly decrease up to 4.95 V in 12.7 hours. In the MATLAB simulation, the battery model shows a similar trend. The battery simulation model was started at 12.05 V and decreased up to 5 V in approximately 12.8 hours.

Figure 9(b) shows the discharge voltage curve for 180 Watt load. The experiment started from discharge voltage at 12.42 V and declined up to 5.41 V in 6.8 hours. For battery discharge simulation, it is started at 11.81 V until the curve decreased into 5 V. The simulation and the experiment curve has a similar decreasing line pattern, however, the battery in the experiment was run out a little bit longer.

The experiment continued with adding 200W of load, as seen in Figure 9(c). The experiment begin with a voltage value of 12.08V then decreased gradually until 3.51V in 32,160 seconds. With a similar trend, the simulation data begin at 11.79V and declined gradually until 5V.

Figure 9. Voltage discharge model vs voltage discharge experiment. (a) 130 W; (b) 180 W, (c) 200 W

B. ANFIS prediction

After the time-series data collection and the model-based condition, the battery monitoring data was examined in the ANFIS prediction. In ANFIS prediction, there are four different loads were used i.e. 130, 180, 200, and 220 Watt. The experiment was repeated two times for each load to obtain two datasets. The two datasets will be used for ANFIS training and testing. the education feature In relation to the ANFIS model, battery voltage at one hour interval (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 hour). This paper used ANFIS architecture with two inputs and a first-order Sugeno fuzzy model

[13,14]. An ANFIS structure and the training process is presented in Figure 10. There are two data input in Figure 10 i.e. x and y , with x being the different load Y is the, and battery voltage. Each load has 5 data represented 5 hours data collection. The target to be predicted in the duration (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 hour) of battery usage. The model obtained from the training process presented at the below part of Figure 10 is the membership function form. This model is then tested with a different dataset without target.

The ANFIS prediction result is presented in Figure 11. The x axis indicate a total number samples for testing data i.e. 20 samples. These 20 samples consist of 4 different load and each load consist of 5 samples. The y axis represent the duration of the battery from 1 to 5 hour. The circle blue is the target and the red solid dot is the prediction.

The training data and the testing data of ANFIS method were collected from each hour discharge time. One hour is labelled as 1, two hour is labelled as 2, etc. A detail of training data and testing data were presented in Tables 3 and 4. Although the total duration of experiment is more than 5 hours as presented in Figure 7, this study used the 5 hours data as preliminary prediction study. The ANFIS prediction is also used for 1 hour usage battery capacity even though the interval can be changed later for future works for example every 30 minutes.

As presented in Tables 3 and 4, four different load were used for the battery experiment. The discharge voltage values of one hour interval were collected from four different load. These data were then used for ANFIS prediction. It can be seen from Tables 3 and 4 that the discharge voltage values were different between the training and testing data. It is because the data were collected from sequential experiment. The authors were collected all the data training from one battery and conduct a similar experiment from another battery for collecting the testing data. Please note that the battery type used in the training and the testing is a similar type battery.

It can be seen visually from Figure 11 that the ANFIS is a potential prediction tool battery remaining life. A detail prediction accuracy of ANFIS method for four different load is presented in Tables 5-8.

Figure 10. ANFIS training process.

Figure 11. ANFIS prediction results.

Table 3. Training features for ANFIS prediction.

Load (Watt)	Discharge voltage	Label
130	12.01	1
130	11.93	2
130	11.84	3
130	11.73	4
130	11.63	5
180	11.97	1
180	11.77	2
180	11.57	3
180	11.34	4
180	10.55	5

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200	11.83	1
200	11.71	2
200	11.53	3
200	11.36	4
200	11.13	5
220	11.62	1
220	11.37	2
220	10.9	3
220	6.58	4
220	4.53	5

Table 4. Testing features for ANFIS prediction.

Load (Watt)	Discharge voltage	Label
130	12.00	1
130	11.89	2
130	11.78	3
130	11.69	4
130	11.53	5
180	11.99	1
180	11.86	2
180	11.68	3
180	11.31	4
180	9.31	5
200	11.92	1
200	11.74	2
200	11.55	3
200	11.29	4
200	10.22	5
220	11.65	1
220	11.42	2
220	11.04	3
220	7.12	4
220	4.04	5

As mentioned previously that the objective of this study is to predict a present capacity (i.e. discharge voltage value) of the battery based on the historical data. Once the discharge voltage value was obtained from the ANFIS prediction and the total duration battery was also known, the remaining battery voltage will be easily calculated using the following equation:

$$R = T - P \quad (3)$$

where R is the remaining battery voltage, T is the total battery capacity (in volt), and P is the ANFIS prediction discharge voltage.

Table 5. ANFIS prediction for 130 Watt load.

Target (hour)	Prediction (hour)	Accuracy (%)
1	0.92	92.04
2	1.99	99.73
3	2.99	99.83
4	3.86	96.51
5	5.07	98.51

Table 6. ANFIS prediction for 180 Watt load.

Target (hour)	Prediction (hour)	Accuracy (%)
1	1.03	96.58
2	1.78	88.79
3	2.49	82.87
4	3.15	78.85
5	4.20	84.04

Table 7. ANFIS prediction for 200 Watt load.

Target (hour)	Prediction (hour)	Accuracy (%)
1	0.69	69.04
2	1.48	74.15
3	2.16	72.12
4	2.99	74.86
5	3.96	79.22

Table 8. ANFIS prediction for 220 Watt load.

Target (hour)	Prediction (hour)	Accuracy (%)
1	0.98	97.63
2	1.83	91.41
3	2.83	94.33

4	4.17	95.66
5	5.03	99.48

V. CONCLUSIONS

A prediction method of battery has been presented in this study. The experiment was designed to obtain the data during the discharge condition. Four different load were included to simulate the real process. The battery was fully charged prior to experiment to make sure that the data were collected in the whole discharge process.

An ANFIS method based on Sugeno's fuzzy logic model was used in this research. In the ANFIS is when training 2 input data and predict 1 output i.e. discharge voltage value. According to the accuracy results, it indicated that the ANFIS method is a potential method for battery prediction. The prediction average for 130 W, 180 W, 200 W, and 220 W is 97.32%, 86.23%, 73.88%, and 95.70%.

In the future works, more load will be utilized and the prediction interval will be varied in narrower interval. Other machine learning methods will be also examined to compare with the ANFIS method.

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